

INVESTIGATIONS ON INTEGRALLY FORMING PROCESS OF CARBON EPOXY TRIANGULAR GRID STIFFENED SHELLS

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents fabrication processes, including preimpregnated filament winding, hand layup and curing in autoclave, for manufacturing carbon epoxy integral isogrid stiffened shells. The quality control of isogrid reinforcement has been discussed. The external pressure loading test results of isogrid cylindrical shells and a triangular grid conical shell indicate that these shells can meet the design requirements of load bearing structure of aerospace vehicle. The weight of isogrid shell is only about 70% of an equivalent structure produced in aluminum alloy. These investigations conclude that the fabrication processes described in this paper are successful and have such merits as stability of performance, simplicity of operating and low cost.

INTRODUCTION

Isogrid stiffened shells are characterized by their high integral stability and structural efficiency. Such shells have relatively high volumetric efficiency, which is advantageous to minimization of size and weight of vehicle. From the late 70's to the early 80's, many investigators studied fabrication processes in different aspects¹⁻². In order to find an integrally forming process to produce these isogrid structures at low cost, in which the reproducibility of products can be ensured and the operations are simple, we have made great many efforts in this field. Our investigations are primarily focused on the forming and the quality control of the isogrid reinforcement which acts as the main load-bearing part. We use preimpregnated filament winding process, in which aluminum alloy molds are used to exert uniform side pressure on ribs and to provide a rather fine flow condition for resin. With these kinds of measures, the quality of isogrid shell has been improved. The mechanical performance of these shells can meet the design requirements of scaled structure test model of aerospace vehicle. On the basis of these investigations, we have found an integrally forming process to manufacture a shell structure of aerospace vehicle which is composed of an isogrid stiffened shell and two end frames. The test results indicate that the fabrication processes described here are successful and have the merits such as stability of performance, simplicity of operating and low cost.

MATERIALS

1. Carbon Fiber and Its Specifications

The carbon fiber used in fabrication is Liao-Yuan Carbon Fiber, which is produced by Liao-Yuan Chemical Factory in China, and its specifications are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Specifications of Liao-Yuan Carbon Fiber

Property	Unit	Value
Tension		
Ultimate strength	MPa >	2800
Modulus	GPa >	200
Ultimate strain	% >	1

2. Matrix

The matrix used in fabrication is composed of 648 Epoxy Resin (Chinese code) and curing agent BF₃ NH₂C₂H₅.

INVESTIGATIONS ON FORMING PROCESS

In the investigation our attention is primarily given to integrally forming of isogrid shells as well as to the forming process and quality control of ribs, and following aspects are emphasized.

1. Quality Control Method of Isogrid Ribs

The width of rib is about 2 mm, the maximum height about 6.5mm. Ribs of this type must be formed in a particular mold on which there are isogrid grooves with proper size. If pressure is applied just only to the top of groove, the composite in the groove can not be pressed into dense form, and the fiber volume content, void content and uniformity of the rib can not be controlled as required. If the composite in the groove can not be pressed uniformly, cavities and loose regions in composite will occur, and the fiber volume content may be too low. The way to resolve such a problem is to improve the grooved mold used in forming ribs, and great attention must be given to pressurizing two side surfaces of a rib and to the flow mode of resin compound (resin and curing agent) during curing. For this purpose, we designed a grooved mold made of aluminum alloy. The mold uses triangularshaped aluminum alloy blocks mounted on the steel die plate to form the grooves of isogrid pattern. During curing pressure downward is applied to the prepreg filaments filled in grooves, and at the same time static pressure which is caused by the thermal expansion of triangular-shaped aluminum alloy blocks will uniformly be applied to the side surfaces of ribs. In addition, excessive resin compound will bleed from the top and bottom of groove simultaneously, and this flow mode of resin compound is helpful to make the matrix uniform and the rib dense. The size of the rib is controlled by the width and height of the groove, and the linearity of fiber is obtained by the tension applied to the preimpregnated filaments during winding. As compared with silicone rubber mold and plaster mold, the aluminum alloy mold is advantageous to the reproducibility of performance, simplicity of operating and low cost.

2. Preimpregnated Filaments Winding

The preimpregnated filaments winding process is a kind of good winding process. After carbon filaments are impregnated with resin compound, they are placed aside for a short period of time to make solvent evaporate. Then the soft impregnated filaments (volatile content is about 1%) are used in winding. It is helpful to control the quality of composite, especially to improve the density of composite.

PROCESS SEQUENCE

The forming process of carbon epoxy isogrid conical shell consists of following steps. First, the isogrid part is fabricated with manual wind-

ing. Then, two end frames and skin are fabricated with hand layup and machine winding. Finally, the integral shell structure is cured in an autoclave.

The isogrid part is fabricated in such a way that the preimpregnated filaments are manually wound and filled into the isogrid-shaped grooves on the mold. The filaments of isogrid part extend into the top frame and the bottom frame respectively to form an integral structure. Then the isogrid part is preformed for next processing. After the previous steps are finished, the skin is fabricated with hand layup and machine winding. The skin prepreg plies are laid up one after another according to the following directions: 90° , 30° , -30° , 30° , 90° . The prepreg ply must be in tension during laying up to prevent it from wrinkling. After every ply is laid up, it is necessary to roll the surface so as to make it in close contact with sublayers and fiber stretch. Then the surface, particularly at the joint portion, is ironed with an electric iron to make two plies contact closer and to eliminate wrinkles. The temperature of the iron must be controlled under 80°C . After the fourth ply is laid up, the skin is bled under the following conditions: vacuum environment, $85-90^{\circ}\text{C}$, 30-40 minutes duration. Then the final ply (in 90° direction) is wound on the surface after the excessive resin compound is cleaned. Finally, the shell structure and the small comparative test specimen are put into an autoclave to cure under the following conditions: 0.4-0.5 MPa curing pressure, 80°C for 30 minutes, 120°C for 30 minutes and 170°C for 2 hours. After cooling down gradually, the product must be demold carefully to prevent it from being knocked and damaged.

SHELL SPECIMENS

Several isogrid cylindrical and conical shell specimens have been fabricated according to the processes described above. The photographs of them are shown in Fig.1 and 2.

Fig.1 Isogrid stiffened cylindrical shell.

Fig.2 Triangular grid stiffened conical shell.

1. Structural Parameters

The parameters of these specimens are listed in Table 2.

Table 2 Structural Parameters of Carbon/Epoxy Isogrid Cylindrical and Conical Shells^{a)}

Series No.	Form	Length L(mm)	Radius R(mm)	Direction of skin plies (deg.)	Rib Parameters			
					Angle (deg.)	Width B (mm)	Height H (mm)	Length S (mm)
1	Cylin.	320	115	90, 50, -50, 50, 90	30	1.9	3.8	52.13
					-30	1.9	3.8	52.13
2					90	1.9	3.8	52.13
3	Cylin.	320	115	50, -50, 50, -50, 50	30	1.9	3.8	52.13
					-30	1.9	3.8	52.13
					90	1.9	3.8	52.13
4	Conic.	380	249 (bottom)	90, 35, -35, 35, 90	30	2.0, 2.0, 2.0	5.0, 5.8, 6.5	41, 45, 49
					-30	2.0, 2.0, 2.0	5.0, 5.8, 6.5	41, 45, 49
					90	2.3, 2.4, 2.5	5.0, 5.8, 6.5	40, 44, 45

a) Half cone angle 9 degrees. The thickness of plies: 90 deg. ply, 2.5mm; others, 0.21 mm.

2. Nondestructive Testing

Both laser holographic and X-radiographic testing have been employed to test the quality of shell structure. Nondestructive testing has been focused on quality of the bond between the isogrid stiffener and the skin as well as other defects of composite.

RESULTS OF EXTERNAL PRESSURE LOADING TEST

The test results are listed in Table 3.

Table 3 Test Values and Theoretical Values of Shell Specimens

Series No.	Test	Value ^{a)}	Theoretical Value		Ratio = $\frac{P(\text{Test})}{P(\text{Theo.})}$	Failure Mode
	n	P(MPa)	n	P(MPa)		
1	4	1.042	4	1.14	0.914	Collapse
2	4	1.059	4	1.14	0.929	Collapse
3	4	0.96	4	1.09	0.881	Collapse
4	5--6	0.94	5	1.00	0.930	Collapse

a) n-- the number of half waves of the buckles in the circumferential direction;

P-- external pressure on the conical surface.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The external pressure loading test results of carbon epoxy isogrid cylindrical and conical shells indicate that the agreement between test values and theoretical values is satisfactory. The weight of isogrid shell is only about 70% of an equivalent structure produced in aluminum alloy, that is, about 30% weight can be reduced.

2. External pressure loading tests show that the fabrication processes described in this paper are successful and applicable for manufacturing carbon epoxy isogrid stiffened shells with two end frames.

3. Mechanical performance requirements of isogrid shell structure are very strict. The investigations on the forming and quality control of isogrid reinforcement, which acts as the main load bearing part, are effective. In the fabrication preimpregnated filament winding and aluminum alloy mold with isogrid-shaped grooves are used. The reason of using such a mold is that the thermal expansion coefficient of aluminum alloy is much larger than that of carbon/epoxy composite, so the pressure caused by thermal expansion can be applied to side surfaces of ribs. All these measures have played an important role in improving the quality of isogrid reinforcement and the load-bearing capacity of shell structure.

4. As compared with silicone rubber mold and plaster mold, in the fabrication of isogrid shells the main advantages of the aluminum alloy mold are high uniformity and reproducibility of products, simplicity of operating and low cost.

REFERENCES

1. Herle J, SAMPE, 20(1975), 31.
2. Penton AP and Freeman VL, SAMPE, 21(1976), 934,